

Image Watermark Removal Model with Image Inpainting and Autoencoder

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Abstract

Image inpainting has been a quite popular topic in recent years, with quite some related research literature. Image inpainting can also be used in a wide range of tasks, such as colorization, missing area reconstruction, uncropping, or even JPEG restoration. Among the tasks mentioned above, we find the task of missing area reconstruction most interesting, as it has very practical use cases, such as unwanted objects like watermark removal from an image. In this project, we utilize a combination of Convolutional Neural Network and Attention mechanism to implement - first - a model of image inpainting techniques and - second - an autoencoder for watermark removal task, with an aim to both create useful and interesting applications and apply concepts learned in the lectures.

1. Introduction

Images shared over the internet - quite often - have watermarks on them in order to protect the creators' intellectual property. Although utilizing computer vision techniques to remove the watermarks for restoring the original images is not encouraged and even potentially illegal, the very same process - solely for educational purposes - still entails plenty of areas that are worthy of being researched and developed. Also, our work can be used for adversarial attacks aims at preventing illegal watermark removal. In this project, we aim at obtaining a most effective method to remove the watermarks on an image by trying different combinations of learning goals (e.g., image denoising, image inpainting, and encoding image representations using autoencoder) and different ways to process the data.

To better formulate, we partition this project into 4 main parts:

1. A GAN based model empowered by Convolutional Neural Network and Attention mechanism [2] is used to create a model that takes in a watermarked image and a mask that covers the exact positions of the watermarks, in order to utilize image inpainting techniques to recover the original image.

2. A GAN based model empowered by Convolutional Neural Network and Attention mechanism [2] is used to create a model that takes in an watermarked image and a mask that covers a certain range of the neighborhood of the watermarks, in order to utilize image inpainting techniques to recover the original image.
3. An autoencoder empowered by Convolutional Neural Network and Attention mechanism (a slight modification to [2]) - along with data processing - is used to encode a watermarked image and decode for the original image.

Section 4 includes more detail for the implementation.

2. Related Work

2.1. Image Denoising

In [1], the authors proposed an idea that it is possible to learn to restore images by only looking at corrupted examples. They show that a single model can learn photographic noise removal based on noisy data only. They also do practical experiments to show image reconstruction can be learned from corrupted observations only. They start with simple noise distributions such as Gaussian, Poisson, Bernoulli and continue to the much harder, analytically intractable Monte Carlo image synthesis noise and sub-Nyquist spectral samplings in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). They proved that simple statistical arguments lead to new capabilities in learned signal recovery using deep neural networks to recover signals under complex corruptions without observing clean signals. Their noise2noise code is re-implemented and edited in this project to serve as a baseline method for removing text watermarks. The quality of output images produced by denoising is later compared to MAT-based methods we tried which will be introduced later in this report.

2.2. Image Inpainting

GAN-based method Instead of extracting information from the single image directly, [7] proposed a semantic image inpainting method that learns the high-level context of training data by encoding the context information using a

GAN, which can predict semantically meaningful content from images with missing patches. Their non-local inpainting method work on images with large and possibly of arbitrary shape missing patches and their method doesn't require the missing regions in the image to be of similar structure or texture as the pixels surrounding the missing part. Although their proposed method is effective, we decided not to follow their approach because we thought training a GAN is too computationally expensive for our project. Also, training a GAN model is not guaranteed to converge, and we might face model collapse issue.

Diffusion models The authors of SEDIT [6], a guided stroke-based image synthesis and editing method, based their model upon a diffusion model generative prior. The method denoise the input images with added Gaussian noise progressively through a stochastic differential equation (SDE) in order to make the synthesized images look more realistic. Unlike existing generative models that leverage conditional GANs, their method does not require additional data collection or model re-training but can still outperform those state-of-the-art GAN-based approaches. Their method The output images of their proposed method appear both realistic and faithful to user input. Another inpainting work using denoising diffusion model is RePaint [5]. Given an arbitrary binary mask, they employed a pretrained unconditional denoising diffusion probabilistic model (DDPM) as the generative prior. They condition the reverse diffusion process of an unconditional DDPM for image inpainting. Their technique doesn't alter or condition on the original DDPM network itself, thus it can output diverse output photo-realistic images of high quality with any inpainting form, and it can also generalize to unseen mask types. Their work outperforms state-of-the-art Autoregressive, and GAN-based approaches. Since we are unfamiliar with Diffusion Probabilistic models, we decided to only utilize the idea of denoising input images, instead of taking the approach based on diffusion models for this project.

CNN-based method For images with irregular-sized missing regions, existing deep convolutional network based image inpainting methods usually use convolutional filter responses which are conditioned on both the valid regions and also the mean values in masked regions. Such methods often produce output with artifacts such as color discrepancy and blurriness and require additional post-processing to reduce those artifacts. [4] proposed a network based on partial convolutions masked only on valid pixels. In their forward pass, the automatic mask generator is applied to update the mask used for the next layer in the network. Their work is especially useful for masks of irregular shapes.

MAT In contrast to applying attention modules to CNNs, transformer is a natural architecture to handle non-local modeling, where attention is a basic component in every block. [2] develop a new inpainting transformers, capable of generating high-resolution complete results for large mask inpainting. They customize vanilla Transformer block to increase optimizing stability and also improve performance, by removing the conventional layer normalization and replacing the residual learning with fusion learning using feature concatenation. They also propose a new variant of multi-head self-attention (MSA), named multi-head contextual attention (MCA) to compute non-local relations only using partial valid tokens to handle possible heavy interactions between all tokens extracted from the high-resolution input. Most of our work in this project is about improvements based on their work.

2.3. Watermark Removal

There exist several watermark removal techniques. [3] is a work of a two-phase multi-task watermark removal approach which performs a coarse watermark localization phase for estimating the mask for watermark and then a refinement state for background restoration. Their coarse-refinement method outperforms other work that localize watermark and restore missing background regions simultaneously. In our project, we take a similar approach. We first use a denoising model for localizing the binary mask for text watermarks we imposed onto the input images, and then we utilized this mask for later missing region image inpainting phase in the workflow.

3. Dataset Collection

We constructed our own dataset for this project since adding watermark to images is not a very complicated task with the help of diverse OpenCV API methods. We used MS COCO 2014 dataset. We wrote a script to add two semi-transparent text watermark of random words onto each image. The rotated angle of the text watermark is a random value between 10 and 20. The location of the two watermarks on each image is also randomly chosen. The watermark's transparency parameter $\alpha = 0.3$. We randomly sample an English word and the rotated angle for watermarks on each image to make the problem more challenging, preventing the model to overfit to the text pattern or watermark location. Initially, the MS COCO dataset consist of images of varying sizes. For training purposes, since training transformer models with our limited computational power is computationally expensive and time-consuming, we later limit the scope of our project by cropping and resizing the images to be of size 512x512. Since the original dataset is too huge for our project, with 82783 images in the training set and 40775 images in the test set, we then randomly sampled 8280 and 3904 images for training and

Figure 1. The workflow and purposes of the denoising model, which will help both restore the original images and create a binary mask on the watermarks by locating the exact position of the watermarks.

testing purposes respectively in this project to test our ideas.

4. Method

We added a watermark detector (watermark mask generator) based on the denoising concepts introduced in [1], in order to have our system locate the watermark and generate a mask to cover the watermarks for image inpainting tasks. Then, soon we realized that apart from locating the watermarks and generating the masks needed, the denoising model also did a good job on removing the watermarks and restore the original images with some statistical operations.

Hence, we decided to take the restored images from the denoising model as a benchmark for comparing with the results generated by the modified version of the MAT models [2].

For all the MAT-based models, we reused the pre-trained weights from the original MAT paper.

4.1. Denoising Model

The denoising model serves two purposes (and the visualization could be found in Figure 1):

1. Using a UNet architecture [1] to denoise the watermarked image by treating the translucent watermarks as noises on the images. The denoised results are basically the original images, which we could use to accurately locate the watermarks by simply subtracting from the watermarked images. After acquiring the location of the watermarks, we apply a threshold to the watermark background images to generate a binary mask for the MAT-based models.
2. The restored (i.e., denoised) images are used to compare with the restored images from the image inpainting models, whose performance would be observed.

Figure 2. The workflow of exact covering with the MAT model as backbone. In this design, we only cover up the exact positions of the watermarks, so that the model could have as much information as possible to infer the values in the covered regions.

Figure 3. The workflow of regional covering with the MAT model as backbone. In this design, we cover up the neighboring regions of the watermarks - to make sure that all watermarks are decently covered - so that the model only focuses on the parts that are not affected by the watermarks at all.

4.2. MAT with Exact Watermark Covering

In this design, the covering of the watermarked images occurs as little as possible, so that the model could have more information to use as a basis to generate the covered regions on the images. Basically, we use the binary masks generated from the denoising model to cover up the exact positions of the watermarks. The work flow could be found in Figure 2.

4.3. MAT with Regional Watermark Covering

In this design, we basically follow the original design and purposed of the MAT paper [2] by covering up large regions without considering the exact positions of the watermarks. We treat this design as a replication of the work mentioned in [2] and take the results as another benchmark for comparing with those generated from other designs. The work flow of this design could be found in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Upper: The design and workflow of the MAT-based autoencoder. In this design, we do not cover up any part of the watermarked image, instead, we directly encode the watermarked image, with an aim at cropping out the watermarked region which would be combined with the input watermarked image to restore the original image.

Lower (Image source [2]): The architecture of the encoder used in the MAT-based Autoencoder. The first part of the MAT model was modified to be used as an encoder.

4.4. MAT-based Autoencoder with Computer Vision Data Processing

In this design, we took the first part of the MAT model [2], which is a GAN model with a fusion of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Transformer blocks (Attention mechanism), to create an autoencoder. The purpose of the autoencoder is to encode the watermarked image with the MAT design and generate a latent vector that includes the information of both unwatermarked parts and watermarked parts (because the watermarks in our datasets are translucent, hence, those watermarked pixels still contains quite some useful information about the original image).

Then, a decoder would be used to reconstruct the original image. However, it’s reasonable to posit that results of the decoded output would be subpar, as the model takes quite some noise. Therefore, we crop out the watermarked regions from the decoded output, which would be combined with the watermarked input image, without the watermark regions, in hope to create a smoother image as the original one.

The design and workflow could be found in Figure 4.

Figure 5. The generated results from our denoising model. From left to right: Watermarked Image, Original Image, Location of Watermarks, Binary Mask for MAT

5. Results

5.1. Denoising model

The result metrics of our denoising model were decent, and we were able to obtain a PSNR value of 36.3, which was decently enough for the data set we used. The generated results could be found in Figure 5.

5.2. MAT with Exact Watermark Covering

The restored images of this design - although not as great as those of the denoising model - were decent, as we could clearly see that a big portion of the watermarked regions were restored with reasonable values. Example results could be found in Figure 6.

However, there was room for improvement. When we look closer, we could still see the outline of the watermarks. And we believed that this happened because of the following 2 reasons:

1. The pre-trained model weights were mainly trained with locations, places, and people’s faces (the Places and Celeb data set), hence, the when it comes to images capturing other types of objects, the model probably wouldn’t be able to make the most reasonable prediction based on its trained parameters and the input images’ context.
2. The exact covering might be a bit too extreme. Even if the model was able to predict some reasonable values (although not exactly perfect) based on its trained parameters and the image context, but we only covered

Figure 6. The generated results from our exact covering model with MAT backbone. From left to right: Watermarked Image, Restored Image

the exact positions of the watermarks, hence, there would be a very obvious difference created by the border of the watermarks.

The metrics obtained from this design were PSNR: 27.4 and FID: 168.9.

5.3. MAT with Regional Watermark Covering

The restored images of this design were clearly worse than the first two methods, as we could easily spot patches that don't really fit into the image. However, for some images, if viewed with distance, the whole picture looks smooth. The example results could be found in Figure 7.

There was surely room for improvement. And we believed that this happened because of the following 2 reasons:

1. Large hole inpainting has always been a hard task, because a large portion of the image was covered up. Even we know some context about the surrounding, what we could only do is to make statistically feasible decisions based on the priors and the given input. Yet, there are billions of combinations of things that could be present in a covered up region, especially for highly detailed images. for example, the zebra image or the image with two giraffes in the samples.

Figure 7. The generated results from our regional covering model with MAT backbone. From left to right: Watermarked Image, Regionally Covered Mask, Restored Image

2. The training data again has a lot to do with the final predicted results, especially for large hole inpainting tasks, because the model would be highly dependent on the previously learned parameters, which are calculated by using the training data set. In the original MAT paper, they mainly used human faces and physical locations to train their model. Hence, it's possible that our model - which used the pre-trained weights from the original MAT - just doesn't know how to make good inference on other types of images, for example, images of wild lives.

The metrics obtained from this design were PSNR: 25.5 and FID: 181.4.

5.4. MAT-based Autoencoder with Computer Vision Data Processing

The restored images of this design were pretty close to those generated by our exact covering method (Section 4.2), but with a slightly subpar performance, as - in general - a larger portion of the watermarks wasn't properly recovered. However, with a closer look, we could tell that the autoencoder indeed did geenrated some reasonable values for the

Method	PSNR	FID
Denoising	36.3	3.45
Exact Watermark Covering with MAT Backbone	27.4	168.9
Regional Watermark Covering with MAT Backbone	25.5	181.4
MAT-based Autoencoder with CV Data Processing	26.5	174.7

Table 1. Performance by methods and metrics

watermarked regions (e.g., with the correct tone of colors, but just not the right alpha value or brightness). The example results could be found in Figure 8.

We have tried some different modifications, including different loss functions, different numbers of layers of the convolutional filters and transformer blocks, but still to no avail. In the end, we figured that the original architecture provided by the MAT paper worked the best. However, due to the constraints of time and resources, we weren't able to conduct enough ablation study on this design, and we do believe that with more research and experiments, a better performance indeed could be obtained.

For the slightly subpar performance, we had a few hypotheses:

1. The watermarks might be affecting the learning and/or prediction process of the autoencoder. The autoencoder already has only a few nodes to store a whole bunch of information, and with the interruption (i.e., the noise) of the watermarks, it might be possible that the model wasn't able to fully learn and store useful patterns and information.
2. It's probably just the best idea to use attention mechanisms in an autoencoder architecture. Although, transformer blocks are good at capturing information among patches and/or pixels that are far away, still when human make sense out of or create images, neighboring patches/pixels (i.e., close-by objects) still play a very important role in perception. Also, the pairwise computing of the Attention mechanism generates way more intermediate results compared to convolutional filters. Then, it's possible that the limited space of the latent vector was not able to contain all the important information from the attention mechanism.

The metrics obtained from this design were PSNR: 26.5 and FID: 174.7.

A table of the summarized results of the metrics could be found in Table 1.

6. Scope for Improvement

In terms of futuristic work for improvements, one area that we would love to dig deeper is definitely the MAT-

Figure 8. The generated results from our MAT-based Autoencoder with Computer Vision Data Processing. From left to right: Water-marked Image, Restored Image

based Autoencoder method with Computer Vision data processing. Statistically and operationally, the method does make sense, and we originally hoped that the results would be close to those generated by the denoising model. However, we weren't able to get close to our goal, and we believe that with more time and resources, we should be able to have improved performance.

One particular aspect we currently thought could make quite some improvement is to change the attention mechanism. If we could somehow give different weighting to different patches that the Transformer takes to calculate attention, then we could assign less weight to the patches that are covered by watermarks, so that the autoencoder would potentially pay less attention to those areas. Additionally, we could also try to identify which patches are covered by watermarks and apply statistical operations on them, in order to minimize the influence of the the watermarks (noises). This idea is pretty close to our denoising model, but the denoising technique is applied within the attention mechanism and on the patch-level instead of image-level.

7. Conclusion

We concluded that - currently with our results - denoising models (or non-inpainting generative models) are probably the best method to go with for restoring images cov-

ered by watermarks, especially translucent watermarks. We believe this is a reasonable statement because the areas covered by watermarks still carry quite some information about the original image, because the watermarks are translucent, and that's perhaps the reason why we had our denoising model performing the best.

Furthermore, image inpainting is probably not the most suitable technique for watermark removal. Watermark removal - intrinsically - requires the exact reconstruction of the original image, however, image inpainting - by its nature - induces quite some randomness into the result generation. This is a cogent point of the fundamental difference between watermark removal and image inpainting, even though conceptually their concepts could match.

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